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Research Article

**DOSSIER FILLING AND COMPARITIVE STUDIES OF
REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS IN CIS COUNTRIES**Shaik Yasmeen^{1*}, Brahmaiah Bonthagarala², G Rama Krishna³, M.V.Nagabhushanam⁴,
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Road, Guntur-522002, A.P., India.**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**ABSTRACT:**

The CIS region has an enormous growth potential market for India. The registration of the drug products in CIS regions is a challenging task because these countries have no harmonized regulatory organization. The CIS region includes 12 countries such as Russia, Kyrgyzstan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia and Moldova, which required different regulatory guidelines for medicinal product registration as per their FDA guidelines. The different guidelines for the same region become a challenging task for the manufacturer and exporter. The registration of the same product for different countries of CIS is not possible with the same dossier due to the lack of their regulatory harmonization. These countries obey their country-specific dossier format, so to target these market manufacturers and exporters needs to submit different dossier documents for different countries. But Ukraine and Kazakhstan have harmonization & it varies in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. Ukraine and Kazakhstan are also getting strict & expecting USFDA level documents for approval

Key words: CIS, Dossier, Regulatory Authorities, USFDA**Corresponding author:****Shaik Yasmeen,**II/II M.Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Regulatory Affairs,
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INTRODUCTION:

The Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) is a regional intergovernmental organization of nine (originally ten, plus two founding non-members) post-Soviet republics in Eurasia. It was formed following the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991. It covers an area of 20,368,759 km² (8,097,484 sq. mi) and has an estimated population of 239,796,010 [1,2].

Flag	Country	Drug Regulatory authority
MEMBER STATES		
	<u>Azerbaijan</u>	Ministry of Health
	<u>Belarus</u>	Ministry of Health
	<u>Kazakhstan</u>	National Centre for Medicines, Medical Devices and Medical Equipment Expertise ^[8]
	<u>Kyrgyzstan</u>	Ministry of Health ^[9]
	<u>Armenia</u>	Ministry of Health
	<u>Moldova</u>	Ministry of Health
	<u>Russia</u>	ROSZDRAVNADZOR(Ministry of Health)
	<u>Tajikistan</u>	Ministry of Health ^[10]
	<u>Uzbekistan</u>	National Information and Analytical Centre on Drugs Control ^[11]
ASSOCIATE MEMBER STATE		
	<u>Turkmenistan</u>	Ministry of Health
FORMER PARTICIPATING NON-MEMBER STATE		
	<u>Ukraine</u>	Ministry of Health ^[12]

The common wealth independent states (CIS) had its origin on December 8, 1991, when the elected leaders of Russia, Ukraine and Belarus signed an agreement forming a new association to replace the crumbling union of soviet socialist republics (U.S.S.R). The three Slavic republics of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan by the

Transcaucasia republics of Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia, and by Moldova. (the remaining soviet republics – Lithuania, Latvia, and Estonia declined to join the organization). The CIS formally came into being on December 21, 1991, and began operations the following month, the city of Minsk in Belarus designated as its administrative centre [3-6].

COMMONWEALTH OF INDEPENDENT STATES

Flag

Emblem

There are nine member states of the commonwealth of independent states:

- **Armenia**
- **Azerbaijan**
- **Belarus**
- **Kazakhstan**
- **Kyrgyzstan**
- **Moldova**
- **Russia**
- **Tajikistan**
- **Uzbekistan**

It also has two associated member states: **1) Ukraine**

2) Turkmenistan

- **Turkmenistan** is an associate member state. It signed the agreement to join the CIS in 1991 but has not ratified the charter.
- **Ukraine** "Founding State". Has never been a member. "Associate state" since 1993.

Table-1-Regulatory Authorities in CIS Member Countries

CIS Requirements	
<i>Site registration</i>	Yes
<i>Plant GMP approval</i>	Audit by CIS member countries of finished product site
<i>Stability Zone</i>	Zones I and II
<i>Stability requirements</i>	25 ⁰ ± 2 ⁰ C, 60% ± 5% RH
<i>Number of submission batches</i>	3 primary batches, out of which min 2 are pilot scale
<i>Stability data</i>	12 months
<i>Stability guidelines reference</i>	ICH
<i>BE Study (for generic)</i>	Reference drug in any country where BE to be done locally. BE to be done against local reference product in some countries.
<i>Major holdup</i>	Legalizations, translations, funds, registration cost, document and time delay
<i>Dossier format</i>	Country specific (resemble CTD)
<i>Registration time</i>	6-24 months (Russia 18 months) and (Belarus-180 working days)

TABLE-2-DATA REQUIREMENTS FOR REGISTRATION OF PRODUCTS IN CIS COUNTRIES

2. PROCESS OF REGISTERING PRODUCTS IN CIS COUNTRIES (RUSSIA)⁷⁻¹²

Two distinct trends can be identified in the development of the regulatory legislation in the CIS countries: some countries, like Ukraine, try to adopt as much as possible of the European/ International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) perspective (although some unexpected consequences have occurred during local implementation, as will be demonstrated by the Ukrainian case study below),

whereas others like Russia continue to go their own way partly because of their USSR heritage.

Since Russia and Ukraine are the two biggest and most attractive CIS markets and have two very different regulatory approaches, this work will be focused mostly on the comparison of the legislation in those two countries with the European Union (EU) regulatory practice. Such a comparison

demonstrating similarities and differences of two worlds is definitely interesting, not only for the Regulatory Affairs employee working in an EU-based pharmaceutical companies or the authorities, but also for their regulatory counterpart in the CIS countries.

CHECKLIST FORM DOSSIER IN CIS CHECKLIST [12-15]:

(Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Moldova, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia.....etc)

Product information

Name of the product

Country

Initiated by

Date of initiation

Checked by

DOCUMENTS TO BE REQUESTED FOR MODULE-1

1. Trade Name Assigned
2. Registration status in other countries
3. Periodic safety reports (PSUR)
4. Risk management plan (RMP)
5. Post marketing clinical data (for injection, Kazak)
6. Art work for all proposed packs
7. Manufacturing license of the manufacturer
8. GMP certificate of the manufacturer (India GMP)
9. GMP certificate of the manufacturer (Russian GMP)
10. Certificate of pharmaceutical product (COPP)
11. Global innovator of this product
12. Innovator in Ukraine (Ukraine specific)
13. Pack style of global innovator

DOCUMENTS TO BE REQUESTED FOR MODULE -2

14. Section 2.4
15. Section 2.5
16. Section 2.6
17. Section 2.7

DOCUMENTS TO BE REQUIRED FOR MODULE-3

18. API DMF from API manufacturer
19. Restricted part of API (optional)
20. API specification from FP manufacturer
21. API standard test procedures from FP manufacturer
22. API COAs from FP manufacturer
23. API COAs from API manufacturer
24. API w.std COA from FP manufacturer

25. API w.std COA from API manufacturer
26. API TSE/BSE certificate from API manufacturer
27. API GMO certificate from API manufacturer
28. Master formula
29. Colorant qualitative & quantitative composition
30. FP product development report
31. Comparative dissolution in multimedia
32. Batch manufacturing record (from current batch)
33. In process specification (just for reference)
34. In process COAs (3 batches)
35. Mfg process validation protocol and report
36. Packaging process validation protocol and report
37. Excipients specifications
38. Excipients standard test procedures
39. Excipients company COAs
40. Excipients vendor COAs
41. Excipients TSE/BSE certificates
42. Finished product specifications
43. Stability specification
44. Finished product standard test procedure
45. Raw data for identification tests
46. AMV for assay
47. AMV for dissolution
48. AMV for related compounds
49. AMV for uniformity of dosage units
50. AMV for water
51. AMV for microbial examinations
52. AMV for identification of colorants
53. FP CoA's (as per current specification)
54. Packing material specification
55. Packing material standard test procedure
56. Packing material company's CoA's
57. Packing material vendor CoA's
58. Primary packing material food grade certificates
59. Batch packing record for proposed pack styles
60. Stability protocol for all proposed packs
61. Accelerated stability for all proposed pack styles
62. Long term stability for all proposed pack styles
63. API COA used for BE studies
64. Section 5.4: literature references

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION:

The generic drug filing in the CIS countries is the one of most demanding in the emerging markets. The primary purpose of the rules governing medicinal products in CIS countries is to safeguard public health. It is the role of public regulatory authorities to

ensure that pharmaceutical companies comply with regulations. There are legislations that require drugs to be developed, tested, trialed and manufactured in accordance to the guidelines so that they are safe and patient's well – being is protected.

CTD provides a globally harmonized format that is accepted in many regions, avoiding the need to compile different registration dossiers for different regulatory authorities. The primary purpose of the rules governing medicinal products in CIS countries is to check whether drugs are manufactured in accordance to the guidelines so that they are safe and efficacious. Countries have different standards, registration costs and long timelines for registration of generic drugs this may account for the good market share.

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